

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE NATURE OF ATTENTION DEFICIT AND HYPERACTIVITY DISORDER IN CHILDREN (PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW)

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Abstract

Attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder causes emotional and social difficulties in children. they have difficulty in controlling their impulsive behavior. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is a disorder of attention, concentration, mobility and impulse control. It is a common psychiatric disease in childhood. Treatment of this disease includes drug and non-drug therapy. Although many treatment methods are applied holistically for a long time, significant improvement is achieved and affects the course of the disease in this direction. For this reason, students, teachers and families need information about the recognition and management of the disease.

Keywords: attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder, correction, psycho-social.

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is one of the most common psychiatric disorders in children. Attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder causes emotional and social difficulties in children. they have difficulty controlling their impulsive behavior. They act without thinking about the consequences of their actions. In addition to the problems it brings to the society, children have poor self-awareness, problems in social relations, failure in their school activities and have a negative effect on their self-confidence. It may present with symptoms of difficulty learning and concentrating, disorganization, forgetfulness, difficulty maintaining attention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity [3]. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder can be observed by families at an early age. In fact, this situation manifests itself clearly when the child starts school. It is possible for parents, coaches and teachers to work together to diagnose and address this condition early. Hyperactivity is a treatable disorder. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder was first identified in the 1900s. In those years, this condition was diagnosed as hyperactivity. In 1971, a researcher named Wender made a diagnosis close to today's attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder.

They have problems such as not being able to control their aggression. The following signs of attention deficit in children come to the fore [4].

- ✓ They have trouble focusing on a task or make careless mistakes in school work.
- ✓ During responsibilities and games; They may have difficulty staying focused
- ✓ When we talk to him, it seems that he does not listen to the adults around him and his parents complain that he does not listen. It always distracts them when they say it out loud
- ✓ Has difficulty following assignments at school or at home. He can't finish his homework
- ✓ Has difficulty organizing duties and responsibilities. It makes things randomly confusing. The room is cluttered with his tableware.
- ✓ Avoids doing tasks that require mental effort for a long time and does not want to do them. .)

- ✓ He is easily distracted by the irritants around him, looks out the window in the classroom
- ✓ He is forgetful in daily tasks and does not complete the tasks that need to be done on his own.

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder usually includes symptoms that can be seen in many children, but the number, duration, and how negatively they affect the child's life are important when making a diagnosis. For a diagnosis, a child must have at least 2/3 of the symptoms in one or both of these two groups. In addition, symptoms must have started before age 7 and cause problems in at least two different settings.

- ✓ Symptoms of hyperactivity: they can't sit when they should, have difficulty playing quietly, run and climb inappropriately, often answer a question without completing it, are always busy with something, they intrude and interrupt events or conversations.
- ✓ Signs of inattention: unable to follow instructions from start to finish, difficulty concentrating on a task or game, losing materials needed for tasks and activities at home or school, not listening when spoken to, difficulty completing tasks that require mental effort for long periods of time, and they avoid them.

Drug correction of ADHD is more commonly used in foreign countries, especially in the United States where the use of drugs is a major concern. Psychostimulants, less often antidepressants and antipsychotics are prescribed for behavioral disorders. However, they have serious side effects (insomnia, irritability, disorders of the cardiovascular system, gastrointestinal tract, headaches, addiction). In 1990, the American Academy of Pediatrics made a decision against the unilateral use of drugs in the treatment of ADHD: education and behavior correction should be carried out..." [6]. The use of psychostimulants is also not allowed in neighboring Russia. [7, 8].

Psychosocial treatment is important in children with hyperactivity and attention deficit disorder. Thus, their impulsivity or communication problems can cause problems in relationships with their peers. By improv-

ing social skills through psychoeducation, it has a positive effect on emotional intelligence, which includes not only the child, but also the family and their environment. It is predicted that the psychoeducation provided for the proper conduct of the relevant processes will have a positive effect on the treatment process [5].

Social Skills Training: In addition to the drug treatment program, it is very important to teach problem-solving skills to children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. And long-term children are taught how to handle problems in everyday life.

Correction of memory disorders:

In complex cases of memory impairment, simple training is ineffective. In order to compensate for the defect, psychologists recommend teaching the child to figuratively imagine what needs to be remembered and to attract various combinations. The psychologist uses the "pictogram" technique in the lessons, which is based on the ability to represent the given material using simple symbols and drawings. As a result of special lessons with the child, this skill becomes automatic, and then it is carried out on an internal level (mentally), without creating drawings.

Correction of attention disorders:

In the correction of attention and self-control disorders, the psychologist's recommendations are aimed at developing the technique of formulating operations to check and evaluate a person's work. The technique of composing small texts with a large number of gross errors is used (this can be spelling or mathematical material). In this case, the child plays the role of a teacher, that is, he corrects mistakes with a red pen. It should be remembered that in this case, the child should not make mistakes in spelling rules that he does not yet know. After the child learns to find at least half of the mistakes, he is asked to make them himself, and after a while to find and correct them. At the next stage, self-control, organized in a playful form, turns into strict self-control of homework, previously checked only by parents.

Thus, prevention and treatment of children with attention deficit disorder should involve pediatricians, psychologists, teachers and parents. All methods of psychocorrection and drug treatment, with timely diagnosis, will help hyperactive children to compensate for

disorders in time and fully realize in life. Non-drug therapy uses an integrated approach involving the work of several specialists: neuropsychologist, psychologist, speech therapist, etc. As a result of multimodal treatment, it will contribute to the child's attention to school activities and to the noticeable improvement of the child's quality of life.

References

1. Barke, J. S. Ve Brandeis, D. (2013). Nonpharmacological Interventions For ADHD: Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses of Randomized Controlled Trials of Dietary and Psychological Treatments, *Psychiatry* 170:3.
2. Willcutt, E. G. (2012). The Prevalance of DSM-IV Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: A MetaAnalytic Review. *Neurotherapeutics*
3. Ozbay, H. C. (2022). Evaluation of the relationship between slow cognitive tempo, attachment and temperament in children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. Aydın Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Child and Adolescent Mental Health and Diseases.
4. Sürücü, Ö. (2019). Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. Bilgi Publishing House.
5. Ozoglu, E. B., & Yuksel, M. (2018). The effect of emotional literacy program applied to 9-10 year old students diagnosed with ADHD on emotional intelligence and attention skills levels. *Marmara University, Ataturk Faculty of Education, Journal of Educational Sciences*, 47(47), 141-156
6. Satterfield J.H., Schell A. A prospective study of hyperactive boys with conduct problems and normal boys: adolescent and adult criminality // *J. Am. Acad. Child. Adolesc. Psychiatry*. - 1997. - v. 36. - № 12. - P. 1726-1735.
7. Gromova O.A., Krasnykh L.M., Limanova O.A. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder - correction possibilities // *Russian pediatric journal*. - No. 2. - 2005. - P. 17-22.
8. Suvorinova E.V. Treatment of children with minimal brain dysfunctions with nootropics // // author's abstract. diss... candidate of medical sciences. - M.- 2000. - 24 p.